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● First record of *Paraleprodera bigemmata* (Thomson, 1865) (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, Lamiinae, Monochamini) from China

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Abstract: *Paraleprodera bigemmata* (Thomson, 1865) is recorded from China (Yunnan) for the first time. Hind wing and terminalia of male are described for the first time. A diagnosis between *P. bigemmata* and *Paraleprodera insidiosa* (Gahan, 1888) is provided.

Keywords: China, hind wings, longicorn beetles, male terminalia, new faunistic records

● 芽斑齿胫天牛 *Paraleprodera bigemmata* (Thomson, 1865) (鞘翅目, 天牛科, 沟胫天牛亚科, 墨天牛族) 首次记录于中国

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摘要: 本文首次记录芽斑齿胫天牛 *Paraleprodera bigemmata* (Thomson, 1865) 分布于中国 (云南), 并首次描述了雄性的后翅和交尾器。提供了芽斑齿胫天牛与瘦齿胫天牛 *Paraleprodera insidiosa* (Gahan, 1888) 的鉴别特征。

关键词: 中国, 后翅, 天牛, 雄性交尾器, 新区系记录

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● Introduction

Paraleprodera Breuning, 1935 presently includes 19 species and 2 subspecies from Asia. Most of taxa are distributed in Southeast Asia, and 8 species and 1 subspecies are recorded from China (Tavakilian & Chevillotte 2025; Liang et al. 2025). Thomson (1865) described *Epicedia bigemmata* from India, then Breuning (1935) described *Paraleprodera assamensis* from India (Assam). Later Breuning (1949) treated *P. assamensis* as a junior synonym of *E. bigemmata*, and transferred *E. bigemmata* to the genus *Paraleprodera*. Presently, *Paraleprodera bigemmata* is only recorded from India.

In this paper, *P. bigemmata* is newly recorded from China (Yunnan), thus 9 species and 1 subspecies are currently recorded from China; besides, the description of hind wings and terminalia of male are presented for the first time.

● Material and methods

The examined specimens are deposited in BMNH (The Natural History Museum, London, United Kingdom) and LPSNU (School of Biological Science and Technology, Liupanshui Normal University, Liupanshui, Guizhou, China).

The methods of taking figure 2 followed Huang *et al.* (2020), figure 3 followed Liang *et al.* (2025). The terminology of hind wings vein followed Švácha & Lawrence (2014). The terminology of male terminalia followed Ślipiński & Escalona (2013).

● Taxonomy

Paraleprodera bigemmata (Thomson, 1865) 芽斑齿胫天牛

Figs 1, 2, 3

Epicedia bigemmata Thomson, 1865: 295 (type locality: “India”); Gemminger 1873: 3012 (catalogue).

Paraleprodera assamensis Breuning, 1935: 255 (type locality: “Assam, India”); Breuning 1943: 154 (key), 268 (description), fig. 143.

Paraleprodera bigemmata: Breuning 1949: 2 (synonym); Breuning 1961: 334 (catalogue).

Type material examined. Holotype of *Paraleprodera assamensis* Breuning, 1935, ♂ (BMNH, examined from four photographs, Fig. 1A–D): Assam. (printed in black ink on a rectangular white label) / Atkinson. Coll. 92–3. (printed in black ink on a rectangular white label) / *Paraleprodera assamensis* mihi Typ. (handwritten) det. Breuning (printed in black ink on a rectangular white label) / Type (printed in black ink on a circular white label with red border) / NHMUK 014016930 plus a QR code (printed in black ink on a rectangular white label).

Material examined. 2♂♂ (LPSNU), Mangyun Village, Taiping Town, Yingjiang County, Dehong Dai and Jingpo Autonomous Prefecture, Yunnan Province, China, alt. 800 m, early June 2019, Shao-Fu Chen leg.; 1♂ (LPSNU, figs 2, 3), Taiping Town, Yingjiang County, Dehong Dai and Jingpo Autonomous Prefecture, Yunnan Province, China, alt. 900 m, 2.V.2019, Chang-Gui Liu leg.; 1♂ (LPSNU), Hulukou (Menglai River Secondary Power Station), Xima Town, Yingjiang County, Dehong Dai and Jingpo Autonomous Prefecture, Yunnan Province, China, alt. 1200 m, VI–VII.2018, Wei-Zhong Yang leg.

Supplementary description of male. Hind wing (Fig. 2E): apexes of these veins (AP₃, AA₄, AA₃, CuA₂, MP₄, MP₃, MS) distant from margin, apex of AV closed to margin. AA₄ vein nearly as long as AA₃ vein, Cu vein connected with AA₃ vein at base of AA₃ vein. CuA₂ vein distinctly shorter than MP₄ vein, MP₄ vein distinctly longer than MP₃ vein, MP₃ vein longer distinctly longer than MP₃₊₄ vein. The r₄ vein with a short spur on the right side of the middle, and r₄ vein connected with RP vein near base of RP vein, RP vein longer than MS.

FIGURE 1. *Paraleprodera assamensis* Breuning, 1935, holotype, male: A habitus, dorsal view B habitus, ventral view C habitus, lateral view D labels (all photographs taken by Zhuo Chen).

FIGURE 2. *Paraleprodera bigemmata*, male (Yunnan, China): **A** habitus, dorsal view **B** habitus, ventral view **C** habitus, lateral view **D** head, frontal view **E** right hind wing, dorsal view (**A** anal **AP** anal posterior vein **AV** veins in apical wing region **Cu** cubital **MP** medial posterior **MS** medial spur **r** radial **RP** radius posterior vein **sr** spur on crossvein **r4**).

Terminalia (Fig. 3A–H): the tergite VIII (Fig. 3A) wider than long, gradually constricted from base to apical 1/3, and abruptly constricted from apical 1/3 to apex, rounded apically; disc sparsely covered with long and short brown hairs from apical 1/3 to apex, sides of base to apical 1/3 with sparser long and short brown hairs. The sternite VIII (Fig. 3B) depressed at apex, with a small notch at apical middle; disc sparsely covered with long and short brown hairs at apical 1/2; spiculum relictum longer than sternite VIII. Stem of spiculum gastrale more than 2.0 times as long as a branch (the long one) of spiculum gastrale (Fig. 3C–D), and apex of the stem curved as a hook. Apexes of both parameres rounded and closed together, both parameres sparsely covered with short and several long brown hairs from basal 1/3 to apex (Fig. 3E–F); phallobase (Fig. 3E) expanded near apical 1/3, apex of each tegminal strut

notched. Penis abruptly constricted near middle in dorsal view (Fig. 3G) and expanded towards venter near middle in profile (Fig. 3H), ventral plate of penis slightly longer than dorsal plate, and truncated at apex, dorsal plate rounded at apex, apex of dorsal struts of penis rounded (Fig. 3G–H).

Diagnosis. This species is similar to *Paraleprodera insidiosa* (Gahan, 1888) (see Fig. 61a in Li & Chen 2020) in each elytron with sparse coarse granules at base, and with a big sub-oval black spot surrounded with a wide pale yellow hair band on the apical half. But *P. bigemmata* can be distinguished from it by the granule near base of elytral middle bigger (without bigger granule in *P. insidiosa*), the area of the spot and the band not beyond elytral middle (distinctly beyond elytral middle in *P. insidiosa*).

Distribution. China (Yunnan), India (Assam).

FIGURE 3. Male terminalia of *Paraleprodera bigemmata* (Yunnan, China): **A** tergite VIII, dorsal view **B** sternite VIII, ventral view **C** spiculum gastrale, dorsal view **D** spiculum gastrale, lateral view **E** tegmen, dorsal view **F** tegmen, lateral view **G** penis, dorsal view **H** penis, lateral view. Not to scale.

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● Additional information

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